

Mesalamine relieves gastrointestinal inflammation in *cis*.

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We examined the hypothesis that 5-aminosalicylates functioned topically in the lumen of the gastrointestinal tract and therefore possessed utility in enhancing clinical success of intravenous monoclonal antibodies that target TNF α in patients with severe disease: by enhancing effectiveness of the IV drug through reducing transmission or propagation of inflammation between the gut epithelial tissues and the hematopoietic compartment, and/or by minimizing the likelihood of developing resistance by modification of the hematopoietic milieu. In patient tissues from humans with the IBD ulcerative colitis, *ex vivo* mesalamine exposure in rectal explants resulted in relief of inflammation through antagonism of interleukin-1 β , of inflammatory cyclooxygenase and eicosanoid synthesis through targeting of the prostaglandin pathway (*PTGS2*) and by suppression of the sphingosine biosynthetic pathway. Mesalamine relieves inflammation in the gastrointestinal tract of humans with IBD and does so directly, in *cis*, through a topical mechanism involving reduction of inflammation through targeting of interleukin, prostaglandin and sphingosine pathways.

Citations

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